

The state of knowledge of the jaguar *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Carnivora, Felidae) during the Quaternary in Uruguay

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ISSN (imprimé / print) : 1631-0683/ ISSN (électronique / electronic) : 1777-571X

The state of knowledge of the jaguar *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Carnivora, Felidae) during the Quaternary in Uruguay

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Submitted on 13 March 2021 | Accepted on 1 June 2021 | Published on 8 September 2022

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:8F56387C-7D5F-4DC8-98D0-EC053A0873AC

Manzuetti A., Jones W., Perea D., Ubilla M., Rinderknecht A. & Toriño P. 2022. — The state of knowledge of the jaguar *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Carnivora, Felidae) during the Quaternary in Uruguay. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 21 (31): 707-720. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2022v21a31>

ABSTRACT

Felids are the top predators in the environments they inhabit. They entered South America at the Pliocene-Pleistocene boundary, but their fossil record in Uruguay, although informative, is scarce. In the present contribution, three new materials (two hemimandibles and an isolated first lower molar) assigned to *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) are described. This material came from Quaternary sediments (Sopas, Dolores, and Libertad Formations) from several localities in Uruguay. Based on this material, different aspects of the paleobiology and paleoecology of jaguars are discussed. Remains of these felids were previously listed but never described; thus, the material analyzed here is the first fossil records reliably determined for *P. onca* in Uruguay. These felids would have shared an ecological niche with other large carnivores during the late Pleistocene in Uruguay, such as saber-toothed cats (*Smilodon populator* Lund, 1842; *S. fatalis* Leidy, 1868), *Puma concolor* Linnaeus, 1771, and short face bears *Arctotherium* Burmeister, 1879; and they would have fed upon medium-sized herbivores, principally in vegetated environments.

KEY WORDS

Felidae,
Panthera onca,
Quaternary,
Uruguay.

RÉSUMÉ

L'état des connaissances du jaguar Panthera onca (Linnaeus, 1758) (Carnivora, Felidae) au Quaternaire de l'Uruguay.

Les félinés sont les principaux prédateurs des environnements qu'ils habitent. Ceux-ci sont arrivés en Amérique du Sud dans la limite Pliocène-Pléistocène, mais leur registre fossile pour l'Uruguay, bien qu'informatif, est rare. Dans la présente contribution, trois nouveaux matériaux attribués à *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (deux hémimandibles et une première molaire inférieure isolée) sont décrits. Ce matériel provient de sédiments quaternaires (formations Sopas, Dolores et Libertad) de divers sites en Uruguay. Sur la base de ce matériel, différents aspects de la paléobiologie et de la paléoécologie des jaguars sont discutés. Les restes de ces félinés ont été précédemment répertoriés, mais jamais décrits, donc le matériel analysé ici est le premier enregistrement fossile de *P. onca* clairement déterminé pour l'Uruguay. Ce féliné aurait pu partager une niche écologique avec d'autres grands carnivores du Pléistocène supérieur de l'Uruguay, tels que les tigres à dents de sabre (*Smilodon populator* Lund, 1842; *S. fatalis* Leidy, 1868), *Puma concolor* Linnaeus, 1771, et les ours à face courte *Arctotherium* Burmeister, 1879, se nourrissant principalement d'herbivores moyens dans des environnements de jungle.

MOTS CLÉS

Felidae,
Panthera onca,
Quaternaire,
Uruguay.

INTRODUCTION

Members of the family Felidae Fischer von Waldheim, 1817 are the best adapted for hunting and are more exclusively terrestrial carnivores within the order Carnivora Bowdich, 1821 (Kitchener 1991; Richard 2005; Prevosti & Forasiepi 2018). They entered South America from North America at the Pliocene-Pleistocene boundary (Ercoli *et al.* 2019; see also Rincón *et al.* 2011; Chimento *et al.* 2014), and also during the climax of the Great American Biotic Interchange (GABI), at approximately 1.8 Ma (early Ensenadan Stage/Age) and during other recent events (Soibelzon & Prevosti 2007, 2013; Woodburne 2010; Prevosti & Forasiepi 2018; Chahud & Okumura 2020). Subsequently, they underwent great diversification and were established as the dominant terrestrial predators of the continent (Chimento 2016; Rodriguez *et al.* 2018).

Several genera are registered in South America, such as the extinct *Smilodon* Lund, 1842; *Homotherium* Fabrini, 1890 and *Xenosmilus* Martin, Babiarez, Naples & Hearst, 2000; and the extant *Panthera* Oken, 1816; *Leopardus* Gray, 1842; *Puma* Jardine, 1834 and *Herpailurus* Severtzov, 1858 (see among others Berta 1985; Kurtén & Werdelin 1990; Mones & Rinderknecht 2004; Rincón *et al.* 2011; Chimento 2016; Prevosti & Forasiepi 2018; Manzuetti *et al.* 2018, 2020; Chahud 2020; Chahud & Okumura 2020).

The genus *Panthera* Oken, 1816 comprises five extant species in the New and Old World (Johnson *et al.* 2006; Werdelin *et al.* 2010). In the Americas, it is represented only by *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758), which is currently the largest carnivore on the continent (Seymour 1989; Diaz 2010; Labarca 2015; Rodriguez *et al.* 2018; Prevosti & Forasiepi 2018; Chahud & Okumura 2020). Widely geographically distributed in pre-1900 historical times (from southwestern United States to Patagonia in Argentina) (Seymour 1989; Swank & Teer 1989; Labarca & López 2006; Ferrero 2008; Zarrate-Charry *et al.* 2009; Moreno & Lima-Ribeiro 2015), its distribution has undergone a significant decline in recent times. Currently, it ranges from northern Mexico to northern

Argentina, although with a patched distribution (Seymour 1989; Swank & Teer 1989; Ferrero 2008; Diaz 2010; Rodriguez *et al.* 2018; Ruiz-Ramoni *et al.* 2020), and is considered extinct in several countries, including Uruguay (Seymour 1989; Swank & Teer 1989; Diaz 2010; González *et al.* 2013; Pereira-Garbero *et al.* 2013; Pereira-Garbero & Sappa 2016; Chahud & Okumura 2020). Thus, the last record of a living jaguar in this country dates from 1901 from northeastern Uruguay (Department of Cerro Largo), which borders Brazil (Pereira-Garbero & Sappa 2016).

In the present contribution, three new fossil materials (two hemimandibles and an isolated m1) assigned to *Panthera onca* are described. This material were recovered from Quaternary sediments (the Sopas, Dolores, and Libertad Formations) of different localities from Uruguay (Santa Lucia River near San Ramon town, and Soca, which are both from the Department of Canelones; and Malo Creek from the Department of Tacuarembó) (Fig. 1). Based on this material, different aspects of the paleobiology and paleoecology of jaguars are discussed.

GEOLOGICAL CONTEXT

The Sopas Formation, which is located in northern Uruguay, is characterized by conglomerates with clay and calcareous matrices, conglomeratic sandstone, siltstone, and sandy siltstone. This unit is predominantly brownish with a thickness of 5-8 m and the sedimentary facies were developed mostly under fluvial and associated depositional contexts (Martínez & Ubilla 2004; Ubilla *et al.* 2016). Based on the mammalian fossil assemblage, this unit is correlated with deposits from the late Pleistocene sequence of the Pampean region (Lujanian Stage/Age, 126-7 ka) (Cione & Tonni 2005; Ubilla *et al.* 2011; Cione *et al.* 2015). Radiocarbon and optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) ages in some outcrops correlate mainly with MIS-3 (60-25 ka), and it also includes outcrops at approximately 14 ka (Ubilla *et al.* 2016). Based on the paleontological content of the Sopas Formation, a wide range of environments can be suggested (lacustrine-fluvial, open areas, semi-forested and dense vegetation) (Ubilla & Martínez 2016).

Fig. 1. — Map showing the location of the findings.

The Dolores Formation, which is mainly located in western and southern Uruguay, in the Santa Lucía River Basin (Ubilla *et al.* 2011; Ubilla & Martínez 2016), is comprised of silty claystones and siltstones, clay deposits, sandstones, and gravel (mudstone). It is generally brownish, with shades of gray-green locally, and a maximum thickness of 10 m. It was deposited in semiarid and cold climatic conditions (Martínez & Ubilla 2004; Corona *et al.* 2013). Several absolute dates based on radiocarbon and OSL/TL methods were obtained for the Dolores Formation, with ages ranging from 30-27 to 11.1-10.5 ka BP (Ubilla *et al.* 2011 and references therein; Ubilla *et al.* 2018). Based on the mammalian assemblage, this unit is correlated with the Lujanian Stage/Age (Upper Pleistocene-Groenlandian) (Ubilla *et al.* 2011 and references therein).

Finally, the Libertad Formation, which extends south of the country, contains wavy surfaces and is characterized by lodolites, loess, and sandstones; it has a reddish-brown coloration, incorporates multiform calcium carbonate, and has a thickness of approximately 30 m. It is assumed that this unit was deposited during the early to middle Pleistocene, mainly by stratigraphic criteria (Martínez & Ubilla 2004), although recent dates are approximately 20-17 ka BP

(Gutiérrez *et al.* 2005; Cid *et al.* 2014). According to the mammalian fossil assemblage, this unit is correlated with the Bonaerian Stage/Age (middle to late Chibanian, 400-126 ka, see Cione *et al.* 2015) and Lujanian Stage/Age (upper Pleistocene-Groenlandian) and was deposited in a savannah-like environment or arid to semiarid conditions (Corona *et al.* 2012).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For comparative analysis, skeletal material of *Panthera onca* and *Puma concolor* Linnaeus, 1771 housed in the FC-DPV were used. Published literature of the aforementioned felids and *Panthera atrox* (Leidy, 1853) from Merriam & Stock (1932); Méndez-Alzola (1941); Currier (1983); Seymour (1989); Ferrero (2008); Christiansen & Harris (2009); Montellano-Ballesteros & Carbot-Chanona (2009); Morales-Mejía *et al.* (2010); Carbot-Chanona & Gómez-Pérez (2014); Chimento & Agnolín (2017); Chimento & Dondas (2017); Rodríguez *et al.* (2018); Ruiz-Ramoni *et al.* (2020) were also used. Dental nomenclature follows Berta (1987).

TABLE 1. — Measurements (in mm) of the fossil material studied (CGF 104, FC-DPV 501, FC-DPV 1890) compared with *Puma concolor* Linnaeus, 1771, *Panthera atrox* (Leidy, 1853) and *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (extant and extinct) specimens. Abbreviations: **N**, number of individuals (for other abbreviations see Material and methods); **OR**, observed range. Data according to Merriam & Stock (1932), Seymour (1989), Chimento & Agnolín (2017), and Chimento & Dondas (2017).

	CGF 104	FC-DPV 501	FC-DPV 1890	<i>Puma concolor</i>		<i>Panthera atrox</i>		<i>P. onca</i> SA (fossil)		<i>P. onca</i> (extant)	
				OR	N	OR	N	OR	N	OR	N
TL	191.6	—	186	113.5-154.8	15	206-318	16	—	—	161-198	11
Hm1	45.3	—	39.5	24.6-33.9	12	46-67.1	16	26-39.5	6	28.9-42.4	12
Bm1	18.4	—	17.1	10.4-14.5	12	20-36.9	16	—	—	12-17.6	12
TRLc-m1	107.6	—	103.9	65-78	12	116.4-156.7	14	—	—	77.3-98.3	12
cAP	—	—	17.4	10.6-15.2	15	21.4-33	40	18-21.4	3	13.2-23.5	112
cML	—	—	18.2	8.2-12.2	15	13.9-21.5	17	14.5-16.4	3	9-17	11
p3AP	17.8	—	—	12-16.6	15	17-21.6	17	17-18.2	2	11.8-16.9	11
p3ML	9.1	—	—	5.5-8.3	15	8.9-13.2	17	8.1	1	4.3-9.2	11
p4AP	24.8	—	—	14.4-17.4	15	25.8-32.3	17	22-24.2	3	15.5-22.2	11
p4ML	11.1	—	—	7.11-9.6	15	12-16.9	17	10-11.2	3	8.2-11.7	12
m1AP	26.6	23.2	23.9	15.7-20.4	15	25.1-34	51	22.4-23.5	6	16.5-24.8	112
m1ML	13.1	10.8	11.6	7-9.5	15	12.5-17.9	50	11-12.5	6	6.7-11.4	11

Body mass estimates were made based on allometric equations formulated for extant felids (Van Valkenburgh 1990; Thackeray & Kieser 1992) using measurements of the first lower molar (Appendix 1). To reduce the bias between the geometric mean and arithmetic mean, a correction factor (the ratio estimator [RE]), that is the ratio between the average observed body masses of the sample and the average estimated body masses from the allometric equation) was used to correct this underestimation (see Smith 1993 and references therein). Body mass estimates of the typical prey species available to *P. onca* and the maximum prey size were calculated using equations formulated for extant felids by Prevosti & Vizcaíno (2006), Hemmer (2007), and Prevosti & Martin (2013) (Appendix 1). To infer the prey size, the average body mass estimate of the carnivore was used. According to data availability, the mean absolute value of the percent prediction error (%PE) and the coefficient of correlation (r) were used as comparative indicators of the accuracy of the prediction of the study variables.

All measurements were performed with digital calipers accurate to 0.1 mm and expressed in millimeters, following von den Driesch (1976) (Appendix 2).

ABBREVIATIONS

Mandible and dental measurements

Bm1	breadth of the mandible at the posterior border of the m1;
cAP	antero-posterior diameter of the canine;
cML	transverse diameter of the canine;
Hm1	height of the mandible at the posterior border of the m1;
m1 AP	antero-posterior diameter of the m1;
m1 ML	transverse diameter of the m1;
p3AP	antero-posterior diameter of the p3;
p3ML	transverse diameter of the p3;
p4AP	antero-posterior diameter of the p4;
p4ML	transverse diameter of the p4;
TL	total length;
TRL c-m1	tooth row length canine-m1.

Institutions

CGF	Colección particular Gonzalo Fierro, Montevideo;
FC-DPV	Facultad de Ciencias-Colección Paleontológica (Vertebrados fósiles), Montevideo, Uruguay.

Other abbreviations

GABI	Great American Biotic Interchange;
OSL	optically stimulated luminescence;
RE	ratio estimator.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

Order CARNIVORA Bowdich, 1821
 Family FELIDAE Fischer von Waldheim, 1817
 Subfamily PANTHERINAE Pocock, 1917
 Genus *Panthera* Oken, 1816

Panthera onca (Linnaeus, 1758)

[*Felis*] *onca* Linnaeus, 1758: 42. — Type locality: “America meridionali” restricted to Pernambuco, Brazil by Thomas (1911).

Felis nigra Erxleben, 1777: 512. — Type locality: “Brasilia et Guiania.”

Felis panthera Schreber, 1778: 384; pl. 99. — No type locality given.

F. [Felis] jaguar Link, 1795: 90. Renaming of *F. onca* Linnaeus, 1758.

Leopardus hernandesii Gray, 1857: 278. — Type locality: “Mazatlan.”

Panthera onca – Fitzinger 1869: 211. First use of current name combination.

Felis jaguarete Liais, 1872: 451. Renaming of *F. onca* Linnaeus, 1758.

Felis jaguapara Liais, 1872: 451. Renaming of *F. onca* Linnaeus, 1758.

Felis jaguatyrica Liais, 1872: 459. Renaming of *Felis nigra* Erxleben, 1777.

Felis centralis Mearns, 1901: 139. — Type locality: “Talamanca, Costa Rica.”

Felis paraguensis Hollister, 1914: 169. — Type locality: “Paraguay.”

Felis notialis Hollister, 1914: 170. — Type locality: “San Jose, Entre Rios, Argentina.”

Felis ramsayi Miller, 1930: 14. Replacement name for *Felis paraguensis* Hollister, 1914.

REFERRED MATERIAL. — CGF 104 (Fig. 2; Table 1), right mandible; FC-DPV 1890 (Fig. 3; Table 1), left mandible; FC-DPV 501 (Fig. 4; Table 1), right m1.

FIG. 2. — **A, B**, CGF 104; right hemimandible. **A**, right lateral view; **B**, occlusal view. Scale bar: 10 cm.

GEOGRAPHIC AND STRATIGRAPHIC LOCATION. — CGF 104, Santa Lucía River near San Ramon town (Department of Canelones), Dolores Formation, late Pleistocene-early Holocene; FC-DPV 1890, Malo Creek (Department of Tacuarembó), Sopas Formation, late Pleistocene; FC-DPV 501, Soca locality (Department of Canelones), Libertad Formation, Pleistocene.

COMPARATIVE DESCRIPTION

The hemimandibles are very robust and the horizontal ramus is high; a marked angle is formed towards the symphyseal region. Mandible FC-DPV 1890, when placed on a flat surface, rests on the symphysis region and angular process, while material CGF 104 has a third point of contact configured by the slightly convex inferior border of the horizontal ramus, which shows great variation in this regard among pantherines (Merriam & Stock 1932; Christiansen & Harris 2009). The angular process in both materials does not project conspicuously backward compared with *Puma concolor* (Merriam & Stock 1932) but is ventrally deflected, as in *Panthera onca* and *Panthera atrox* (Christiansen & Harris 2009); the condyles are markedly

transverse. In CGF 104, the coronoid process is robust and, in lateral view, does not sweep backward behind the condyle, as observed mainly in *P. onca* and *P. concolor*, and it differs from *P. atrox*, which often clearly does (Merriam & Stock 1932; Christiansen & Harris 2009). The masseteric fossa in both materials is deep and barely reaches the posterior border of the m1, as observed in *P. onca* and *P. concolor*, while in *P. atrox* it reaches at most the middle part of the m1 (Merriam & Stock 1932). In the labial face of each mandibular ramus, the characteristic foramina of the large extant felids are observed (Méndez-Alzola 1941). The dentition is markedly hypercarnivore. In CGF 104, the canine is not preserved, although, based on the size of the alveolus, it is inferred to be a large tooth; in FC-DPV 1890, the canine is very robust. In occlusal view, it shows a rounded shape, as observed in *P. onca*, but it differs from *P. concolor*, which is more oval (Morales-Mejía *et al.* 2010). Unfortunately, due to its preservation, it is very difficult to identify some diagnostic characteristics, such as the lateral crest. The premolars of the CGF 104 material are

FIG. 3. — **A, B**, FC-DPV 1890; left hemimandible: **A**, left lateral view; **B**, occlusal view. Scale bar: 10 cm.

similar in form but with a remarkable difference in size. The principal cusp in each premolar (the protoconid) is directed upwards with a slight inclination in a posterior way. In the m1 of both materials (CGF 104 and FC-DPV 1890) and in the FC-DPV 501 specimen, both cusps are nearly equal in size in a similar way as observed in *P. onca* or *P. concolor* (Méndez-Alzola 1941); moreover, in *P. atrox*, the protoconid is larger, almost twice the length in some cases, than the paraconid (Montellano-Ballesteros & Carbot-Chanona 2009; Carbot-Chanona & Gómez-Pérez 2014; Chimento & Agnolín 2017). Additionally, the protoconid is higher than the paraconid; in its distal portion, the development of a tiny talonid is observed.

REMARKS

According to the absolute size, the material studied here is quite larger than those of *Puma concolor* and in general is smaller than *Panthera atrox*, being within the expected range of values observed for *Panthera onca* (Table 1; see Merriam & Stock 1932; Méndez-Alzola 1941; Seymour 1989; Ferrero 2008; Morales-Mejía *et al.* 2010; Chimento & Agnolín 2017; Chimento & Dondas 2017). However, for CGF 104, some of these measurements (p3 and m1) are in the lower values reported for *P. atrox* (Merriam & Stock 1932; Montellano-Ballesteros & Carbot-Chanona 2009; Carbot-Chanona & Gómez-Pérez 2014; Chimento & Agnolín 2017 among others).

Body mass estimates for the CGF 104 material show that this animal weighed up to 173 kg (Table 2) according to the equation from Thackeray & Kieser (1992), which has a smaller % PE and thus would have a better prediction range (see Supplementary Material 1). For material FC-DPV 1890 and FC-DPV 501, the body mass estimates were clearly over 100 kg (Table 2).

On the other hand, the body mass of the potential prey for material CGF 104 is over 250 kg and up to 360 kg, and the largest prey size is over 800 kg (Table 3). For the other two materials, the typical prey mass is less than 200 kg, and the maximum prey body mass is between 500–600 kg (Table 3). In any case, it is worth noting that all estimations of body mass made for extinct taxa should be considered with caution and taken as a relative approach rather than absolute values (Prevosti & Vizcaíno 2006; Losey *et al.* 2017, see also Manzuetti *et al.* 2020).

DISCUSSION

ANATOMICAL COMMENTS AND PALEONTOLOGICAL RECORD
Mandibular and dental morphology is, in general, quite similar in most pantherines and, according to the reported variation, has many shared characteristics among the species of the genus

TABLE 2. — Body mass estimation (in kg) based on antero-posterior diameter of the m1 (m1AP). Mean body mass: CGF 104, 168.7; FC-DPV 1890, 119.6; FC-DPV 501, 108.7.

	According to equation from Van Valkenburgh (1990)	According to equation from Thackeray & Kieser (1992)
CGF 104	164.1	173.2
FC-DPV 1890	118.4	120.7
FC-DPV 501	108.1	109.2

(Christiansen & Harris 2009). In particular, the combination of some morphological characteristics, along with measurements, of the material studied here are congruent with the variability recognized in *Panthera onca*. The most important anatomical characteristics of fossils useful to differentiate them from other large conical toothed cats, such as *Puma concolor* and *Panthera atrox*, are as follows: the angular process does not project conspicuously backward, the coronoid process does not extend posteriorly to the condyle, the masseteric fossa reaches the posterior end of m1, the general shape of the canine, and m1 cusps (paraconid and protoconid) of similar size. Moreover, this material correspond to large specimens for the species (in particular the material CGF 104). In addition, the proportions of the p3 and p4 are used as diagnostic characteristics to discriminate among some pantherines (see Hemmer *et al.* 2010). In this way, the size of the p3 is in the measurement range for *P. onca* and *P. atrox*; moreover, the p4 length is intermediate between these two taxa (smaller than *P. atrox* and slightly larger than *P. onca*), but its thickness is clearly jaguar-sized (see Table 1).

The fossil record of *P. onca* in the Americas is quite scarce (Diaz 2010; Chahud & Okumura 2020). The oldest remains assigned to the species come from early to middle Pleistocene sediments from North America (Seymour 1989; Diaz 2010; Rodriguez *et al.* 2018; Ruiz-Ramoni *et al.* 2020). However, there is no agreement about the oldest record in South America (see, among others, Ferrero 2008; Diaz 2010; Cruz *et al.* 2012; Labarca 2015; Rodriguez *et al.* 2018). For instance, according to Van Valkenburgh (1991) and Berman (1994), *P. onca* has been recorded since the Ensenadan Stage/Age (Gelasian-Early Chibanian, 2.58-0.4 Ma, see Cohen *et al.* 2013, 2020), including the Pampean Region of Argentina, but according to Seymour (1989) and Arroyo-Cabrales (2002), *P. onca* entered the late Pleistocene. During the late Pleistocene-early Holocene, it was also recorded in Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Peru, Uruguay, and Venezuela (Ubilla *et al.* 2004; Labarca & López 2006; Ferrero 2008; Shockey *et al.* 2009; Cruz *et al.* 2012; Rodrigues *et al.* 2014; Rodriguez *et al.* 2018; Chahud & Okumura 2020 among others). On the other hand, two extinct subspecies, larger than modern jaguars, are recognized: the North American *P. o. augusta* (Leidy, 1872) (see Seymour 1989; Ruiz-Ramoni *et al.* 2020; Chahud & Okumura 2020) and the southern South American *P. o. mesembrina* Cabrera, 1934, the so-called Patagonian Jaguar (see Labarca 2015; Martin 2016; Prevosti & Forasiepi 2018 among others); however, the taxonomic status

FIG. 4. — A-C, FC-DPV 501; right m1: A, external view; B, inner view; C, occlusal view. Scale bar: 3 cm.

of the latter is under debate. In this way, Cione *et al.* (2009) considered *P. o. mesembrina* indistinguishable from extant jaguars. Moreover, Metcalf *et al.* (2016) found, based on mitochondrial sequences, that the *P. onca* of the Pleistocene of South American Patagonia was genetically different from the modern jaguar but more closely related to it than to Old World pantherines; thus, it represents the extinct subspecies *P. onca mesembrina*. However, according to Chimento & Agnolín (2017), these remains, based on anatomy and its size, correspond to the American lion *P. atrox*, so its taxonomic status is far from resolved.

Although fossil remains of these felids have been previously listed on Uruguayan faunal lists (see Ubilla & Perea 1999;

TABLE 3. — Body mass estimation (in kg) of the typical prey (TPM) and maximum prey (MPM) for the studied material.

	According to equation from Prevosti & Vizcaíno (2006)		According to equation from Prevosti & Martin (2013)		According to equation from Hemmer (2007)
	TPM	MPM	TPM	MPM	TPM
CGF 104	252.6	887.1	323.4	826.3	362.6
FC-DPV 501	111.5	503.2	164.4	532.4	156.1
FC-DPV 1890	133.2	569.2	190.4	585.8	187.5

Ubilla *et al.* 2004), to date, no material of such species have been reliably described. Thus, the present remains are the first properly documented fossil records of this taxon for the country. Moreover, the material studied here along with some remains from Buenos Aires Province (Argentina) (see Seymour 1989; Ferrero 2008; Cruz *et al.* 2012; Moreno & Lima-Ribeiro 2015; Rodríguez *et al.* 2018), considering that the *P. o. mesembrina* remains could correspond to *P. atrox* (see above), would be at the southernmost limit of the distribution of the representative fossils of the species.

PALEOECOLOGICAL ASPECTS AND BODY MASS

Currently, *Panthera onca* lives mainly in tropical conditions within dense vegetation near water sources (rivers, creeks, etc.) or swampy areas, although they show wide environmental tolerance (Seymour 1989; Swank & Teer 1989; Ferrero 2008; Diaz 2010; Rodrigues *et al.* 2014; Moreno & Lima-Ribeiro 2015; Chahud & Okumura 2020). In its distribution range, the species compete for food with another large felid, namely, *Puma concolor*, although their interactions are minimal, and they seem to mutually avoid each other (Seymour 1989 and references therein; Harmsen *et al.* 2009; Romero-Muñoz *et al.* 2010; Rueda *et al.* 2013; Ávila-Nájera *et al.* 2020). However, when both felids are sympatric, *P. concolor* is more abundant in dry areas, while *P. onca* prefers more humid areas (Seymour 1989 and references therein). Additionally, temporal separation has been reported between these two felids (Harmsen *et al.* 2009; Romero-Muñoz *et al.* 2010; Ávila-Nájera *et al.* 2020), and in addition to the aforementioned, jaguars generally show a greater dependence on larger prey than pumas (Romero-Muñoz *et al.* 2010; Payán Garrido & Soto Vargas 2012; Rueda *et al.* 2013; Ávila-Nájera *et al.* 2020). Therefore, it is expected that a segregation pattern based on spatiotemporal distribution and prey preference has probably occurred in the past.

Moreover, these felids coexisted during the late Pleistocene in South America, in addition to *P. concolor*, with other large carnivorous mammals, such as saber-toothed cats (*Smilodon fatalis* Leidy, 1868; *S. populator* Lund, 1842), short face bears (*Arctotherium* Burmeister, 1879), and large canids (*Aenocyon* (synonym of *Canis*) *dirus* (Leidy, 1858), see Perri *et al.* 2021; *Protocyon troglodytes* (Lund, 1838) (see Prevosti *et al.* 2009; Prevosti & Forasiepi 2018; Manzuetti *et al.* 2018, 2020). However, according to differences in body mass, trophic segregation could be inferred between *P. onca* and the cited carnivores, so the competition among them would be limited (see Prevosti & Martin 2013; Bocherens *et al.* 2016).

The diet of *P. onca* includes medium to large mammals, up to 600 kg, but they also show a marked preference for reptiles, particularly caimans, lizards, turtles, boas, and anacondas (Seymour 1989; Swank & Teer 1989; Prevosti & Vizcaíno 2006; Payán Garrido & Soto Vargas 2012). In this context, and according to our results of typical prey mass, *Tayassu pecari* (Link, 1795), *Hydrochoerus* Brisson, 1762, *Tapirus terrestris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Lama* (*Vicugna*) Molina, 1782, *Equus neogeus* Lund, 1840, *Hippidion* Roth, 1899 and *Mazama Rafinesque*, 1817, among others, are recorded in late Pleistocene strata in the territory of current Uruguay (Prevosti *et al.* 2009 and references therein; Ubilla & Martínez 2016), so the possibility that some of these species could have been potential prey of *P. onca* cannot be ruled out.

Finally, body mass estimates for the CGF 104 material greatly surpass the known body mass for most extant individuals of the species (for males, 37-121 kg; for females, 31-100 kg; see Sunquist & Sunquist 2009 and references therein; however, individuals of 130 kg to 158 kg are occasionally reported; see Seymour 1989 and references therein) and are more congruent with fossil remains assigned to this taxon (Prevosti & Martin 2013). For the remaining materials, those values are above the range of females of the species but within the known body mass range for this taxon (Sunquist & Sunquist 2009), particularly towards the larger sizes of the species.

Based on the larger size and body mass of the members of the populations living in the Pleistocene, these felids could potentially hunt larger prey than extant individuals, including juvenile mega mammals (Prevosti & Vizcaíno 2006, see also Prevosti & Martin 2013). The estimation of the body mass of the maximum prey reported here (particularly for material CGF 104) could, to some extent, be indicative of such predatory behavior, but prey preferences of an apex predator are conditioned by a complex combination of factors, such as the size of prey, availability, prey density, and scavenging activities (Schaller 2009). Compared with other solitary felid predators, extant jaguars show an unusually low predator-to-prey body mass ratio, which means that they tend to kill prey slightly smaller than themselves (Hayward *et al.* 2016). In this way, the predation of jaguars over megafauna species could be unusual, and they most likely focused their efforts on smaller animals available within the late Pleistocene herbivore assemblage. This condition, along with the effect of megafaunal extinction and reduction of jaguar body mass at the end of the Pleistocene, suggests that the predatory jaguar ecology has been substantially altered since then (Hayward *et al.* 2016). Additionally,

it was observed that jaguars can use both medium- and large-sized prey that are available and behaviorally vulnerable (González & Miller 2002). Thus, the prey plasticity displayed by *P. onca* may have contributed to their survival to the present (see Hayward *et al.* 2016).

CONCLUSIONS

The material described here, based on morphology and measurements, are assigned to large individuals of *Panthera onca*. These remains are the first fossil materials of this taxon reliably determined for Uruguay and additionally represent the southern limit of its distribution during the Pleistocene in South America. Currently, *P. onca* is the apex predator in South America, inhabiting mainly environments with vegetative cover. During the late Pleistocene in the territory of Uruguay, a large carnivore guild was integrated, potentially hunting upon medium-size mammals.

Acknowledgements

Gonzalo Fierro for collecting and allowing the study of the material CGF 104. Alejandra Rojas (FC-DPV) for allowing the study of the material under their care and for comparative sample. José Coronel participates in the finding of material FC-DPV 501. Associate Editor Lorenzo Rook, and the reviewers (Damián Ruiz Ramoni and another anonymous) for useful comments. Contribution to the Ph.D. Project PEDECIBA Biología of Aldo Manzuetti (Grant ANII POS_NAC_2018_1_151199) and CSIC-C-211-348 (M. Ubilla).

REFERENCES

- ARROYO-CABRALES J. 2002. — Registro fósil del jaguar, in MEDELLÍN R., EQUINGUA C., CHETKIEWICZ C., CRAWSHAW JR. P., RABINOWITZ A., REDFORD K., ROBINSON J., SANDERSON E. & TABER A. (eds), *El jaguar en el nuevo milenio, Fondo de cultura Económica, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México*. Wildlife Conservation Society, México: 343-354.
- ÁVILA-NÁJERA D. M., CHÁVEZ C., PÉREZ-ELIZALDE S., PALACIOS-PÉREZ J. & TIGAR B. 2020. — Coexistence of jaguars (*Panthera onca*) and pumas (*Puma concolor*) in a tropical forest in south-eastern Mexico. *Animal Biodiversity and Conservation* 43 (1): 55-66. <https://doi.org/10.32800/abc.2020.43.0055>
- BERMAN W. E. 1994. — *Los carnívoros continentales (Mammalia, Carnivora) del Cenozoico en la provincia de Buenos Aires*. Unpublished PhD thesis, Facultad de Ciencias Naturales y Museo, Universidad Nacional de La Plata, La Plata, 412 p.
- BERTA A. 1985. — The status of *Smilodon* in North and South America. *Contributions in Science. Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County* 370: 1-15.
- BERTA A. 1987. — The sabercat *Smilodon gracilis* from Florida and a discussion of its relationships (Mammalia, Felidae, Smilodontini). *Bulletin of the Florida State Museum, Biological Sciences* 31 (1): 1-63.
- BOCHERENS H., COTTE M., BONINI R., SCIAN D., STRACCIA P., SOIBELZON L. & PREVOSTI F. 2016. — Paleobiology of sabretooth cat *Smilodon populator* in the Pampean Region (Buenos Aires Province, Argentina) around the Last Glacial Maximum: insights from carbon and nitrogen stable isotopes in bone collagen. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 499: 463-474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2016.02.017>
- CABRERA A. 1934. — Los yaguares vivientes y extinguidos de la América austral. *Notas Preliminares del Museo de la Plata* 2: 34-50.
- CARBOT-CHANONA G. & GÓMEZ-PÉREZ L. E. 2014. — Nueva evidencia de *Panthera atrox* (Mammalia, Felidae) en el Pleistoceno Tardío de Chiapas. *Lacandonia* 8 (2): 83-89.
- CHAHUD A. 2020. — Occurrence of the sabretooth cat *Smilodon populator* (Felidae, Machairodontinae) in the Cuvieri cave, eastern Brazil. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 23 (2): a24. <https://doi.org/10.26879/1056>
- CHAHUD A. & OKUMURA M. 2020. — The presence of *Panthera onca* Linnaeus 1758 (Felidae) in the Pleistocene of the region of Lagoa Santa, State of Minas Gerais, Brazil. *Historical Biology* 33 (10): 2496-2503. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2020.1808975>
- CHIMENTO N. 2016. — Sistemática y relaciones filogenéticas de la familia Felidae en América del Sur, in AGNOLIN F., LIO G., BRISSÓN EGLI F., CHIMENTO N. & NOVAS F. (eds), *Historia Evolutiva y Paleobiogeográfica de los Vertebrados de América del Sur*. Contribuciones del MACN, Buenos Aires: 373-383.
- CHIMENTO N. & AGNOLIN F. 2017. — The fossil American lion (*Panthera atrox*) in South America: Palaeobiogeographical implications. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 16 (8): 850-864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2017.06.009>
- CHIMENTO N. & DONDAS A. 2017. — First Record of *Puma concolor* (Mammalia, Felidae) in the Early- Middle Pleistocene of South America. *Journal of Mammalian Evolution* 25: 381-389. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10914-017-9385-x>
- CHIMENTO N., DERGUY M. & HEMMER H. 2014. — *Puma (Herpailurus) pumoides* (Castellanos, 1958) nov. comb. Comentarios sistemáticos y registro fósil. *Estudios Geológicos* 30 (2): 92-134.
- CHRISTIANSEN P. & HARRIS J. 2009. — Craniomandibular morphology and phylogenetic affinities of *Panthera atrox*: implications for the evolution and paleobiology of the lion lineage. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 29 (3): 934-945. <https://doi.org/10.1671/039.029.0314>
- CID A., ANJOS R., ZAMBONI C., CARDOSO R., MUNIZ M., CORONA A., VALLADARES D., KOVACS L., MACARIO K., PEREA D., GOSO AGUILAR C. & VELAZCO H. 2014. — Na, K, Ca, Mg, and U-series in fossil bone and the proposal of a radial diffusion-adsorption model of uranium uptake. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 136: 131-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2014.05.018>
- CIONE A. & TONNI E. 2005. — Bioestratigrafía basada en mamíferos del Cenozoico superior de la región Pampeana, in DE BARRIO R., ETCHEVERRY R.O., CABALLÉ M. & LLAMBÍAS E. (eds), *Geología y Recursos Minerales de la Provincia de Buenos Aires*. Relatorio del XVI Congreso Geológico Argentino. Asociación Geológica Argentina, La Plata: 183-200.
- CIONE A., TONNI E. & SOIBELZON L. 2009. — Did Humans Cause the Late Pleistocene-Early Holocene Mammalian Extinctions in South America in a Context of Shrinking Open Areas?, in HAYNES G. (ed.), *American Megafaunal Extinctions at the End of the Pleistocene*. Springer, Dordrecht: 125-144. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8793-6_7
- CIONE A., GASPARINI G., SOIBELZON E., SOIBELZON L. & TONNI E. 2015. — *The Great American Biotic Interchange: a South American perspective*. Springer Earth System Sciences, Dordrecht, 97 p. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9792-4>
- COHEN K. M., FINNEY S. M., GIBBARD P. L. & FAN J.-X. 2013. — The ICS International Chronostratigraphic Chart. *Episodes* 36 (3): 199-204. <https://doi.org/10.18814/epiiugs/2013/v36i3/002>
- COHEN K. M., HARPER D.A.T. & GIBBARD P. L. 2020. — ICS International Chronostratigraphic Chart 2020/03. *International Commission on Stratigraphy, IUGS*. Available at: www.stratigraphy.org

- CORONA A., PEREA D., TORIÑO P. & GOSO C. 2012. — Taphonomy, sedimentology and chronology of a fossiliferous outcrop from the continental Pleistocene of Uruguay. *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Geológicas* 29 (2): 514-525.
- CORONA A., PEREA D. & McDONALD G. 2013. — *Catonyx cuvieri* (Xenarthra, Mylodontidae, Scelidotheriinae) from the late Pleistocene of Uruguay, with comments regarding the systematics of the subfamily. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 33 (5): 1214-1225. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.2013.764311>
- CRUZ L., FERNICOLA J., CARIGNANO C. & BARGO S. 2012. — Asociaciones faunísticas del Cuaternario de San Francisco, provincia de Córdoba, Argentina. Implicancias bioestratigráficas y taxonómicas. *Ameghiniana* 49 (4): 642-656. <https://doi.org/10.5710/AMGH.27.11.2011.516>
- CURRIER M. 1983. — *Felis concolor*. *Mammalian Species* 200, 7 p. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3503951>
- DIAZ N. 2010. — New historical records of the jaguar (*Panthera onca*) in Patagonia. *Revista Mexicana de Mastozoología* 14: 23-45. <https://doi.org/10.22201/ie.20074484e.2010.14.1.25>
- ERCOLI M., RAMÍREZ M., MORALES M., ÁLVAREZ A. & CANDELA A. 2019. — First record of carnivora (Puma lineage, Felidae) in the Uquía Formation (late Pliocene-early Pleistocene, NW Argentina) and its significance in the Great American Biotic Interchange. *Ameghiniana* 56 (3): 195-212. <https://doi.org/10.5710/AMGH.31.03.2019.3206>
- FERRERO B. 2008. — Primer registro de *Panthera onca* Linnaeus 1758 (Carnivora: Felidae) en el Pleistoceno tardío de la provincia de Entre Ríos, Argentina. *Temas de la Biodiversidad del Litoral III. F.G. Aceñolaza (Coordinador- Editor)*. INSUGEO, Miscelánea 17: 31-40.
- GONZÁLEZ C. A. L. & MILLER B. J. 2002. — Do jaguars (*Panthera onca*) depend on large prey?. *Western North American Naturalist* 62 (2): 218-222.
- GONZÁLEZ E., MARTÍNEZ-LANFRANCO J., JURI E., RODALES A., BOTTO G. & SOUTULLO A. 2013. — Mamíferos, in SOUTULLO A., CLAVIJO C. & MARTÍNEZ-LANFRANCO J. (eds), *Especies prioritarias para la Conservación en Uruguay. Vertebrados, moluscos continentales y plantas vasculares*. Sistema Nacional de Áreas Protegidas/ Dirección Nacional de Medio Ambiente/Ministerio de Vivienda, Ordenamiento Territorial y Medio Ambiente/Dirección de Innovación, Ciencia y Tecnología/Ministerio de Educación y Cultura, Montevideo: 175-207.
- GUTIÉRREZ M., ALBERDI M. T., PRADO J. L. & PEREA, D. 2005. — Late Pleistocene *Stegomastodon* (Mammalia, Proboscidea) from Uruguay. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie Monatshefte* 11: 641-662. <https://doi.org/10.1127/njgpm/2005/2005/641>
- HAMMER O., HARPER D. & RYAN P. D. 2001. — PAST: Paleontological Statistics software package for education and data analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4 (1), 9 p.
- HARMSSEN B., FOSTER R., SILVER S., OSTRO L. E. T. & DONCASTER C. 2009. — Spatial and temporal interactions of sympatric Jaguars (*Panthera onca*) and Pumas (*Puma concolor*) in a Neotropical forest. *Journal of Mammalogy* 90 (3): 612-620. <https://doi.org/10.1644/08-MAMM-A-140R.1>
- HAYWARD M. W., KAMLER J. F., MONTGOMERY R. A., NEWLOVE A., ROSTRO-GARCÍA S., SALES L.P. & VAN VALKENBURGH B. 2016. — Prey Preferences of the Jaguar *Panthera onca* Reflect the Post-Pleistocene Demise of Large Prey. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 3 (148), 19 p. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2015.00148>
- HEMMER H. 2007. — Saber-tooth cats and cave lions – from fossils to felid performance and former living communities. *Courier Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg* 259: 1-12.
- HEMMER H., KAHLKE R.-D. & VEKUA A. K. 2010. — *Panthera onca georgica* ssp. nov. from the Early Pleistocene of Dmanisi (Republic of Georgia) and the phylogeography of jaguars (Mammalia: Carnivora: Felidae). *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen* 257 (1): 115-127. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0077-7749/2010/0067>
- JOHNSON W. E., EIZIRIK E., PECON-SLATTERY J., MURPHY W. J., ANTUNES A., TEELING E. & O'BRIEN S. J. 2006. — The Late Miocene radiation of modern Felidae: a genetic assessment. *Science* 311 (5757): 73-77. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1122277>
- KITCHENER A. 1991. — *The Natural History of the Wild Cats*. Cornell, University Press, New York, 280 p.
- KURTÉN B. & WERDELIN L. 1990. — Relationships between North and South American *Smilodon*. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 10 (2): 158-169. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.1990.10011804>
- LABARCA R. 2015. — La meso y megafauna terrestre extinta del Pleistoceno de Chile. *Publicación Ocasional del Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, Chile* 63: 401-465.
- LABARCA R. & LÓPEZ P. 2006. — Los mamíferos finopleistocénicos de la Formación Quebrada Queereo (IV Región Chile): biogeografía, bioestratigrafía e inferencias paleoambientales. *Mastozoología Neotropical* 13 (1): 89-101.
- LOSEY R. J., MCLACHLIN K., NOMOKONOVA T., LATHAM K. & HARRINGTON L. 2017. — Body mass estimates in Dogs and North American Gray Wolves using limb element dimensions. *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* 27 (2): 180-191. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oa.2528>
- MANZUETTI A., PEREA D., UBILLA M. & RINDERKNECHT A. 2018. — First record of *Smilodon fatalis* Leidy, 1868 (Felidae, Machairodontinae) in the extra-Andean region of South America (late Pleistocene, Sopas Formation), Uruguay: Taxonomic and paleobiogeographic implications. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 180: 57-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2017.11.024>
- MANZUETTI A., PEREA D., JONES W., UBILLA M. & RINDERKNECHT A. 2020. — An extremely large saber-tooth cat skull from Uruguay (late Pleistocene-early Holocene, Dolores Formation): body size and paleobiological implications. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology* 44 (2): 332-339. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03115518.2019.1701080>
- MARTIN F. 2016. — Cueva del Milodón. The hunting grounds of the Patagonian panther. *Quaternary International* 466 Part B: 212-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2016.05.005>
- MARTÍNEZ S. & UBILLA M. 2004. — El Cuaternario en Uruguay, in VEROSLAVSKY G., UBILLA M. & MARTÍNEZ S. (eds), *Cuenas Sedimentarias de Uruguay. Geología, Paleontología y recursos naturales. Cenozoico*. Ediciones D.I.R.A.C. Universidad de la República- Facultad de Ciencias, Montevideo: 195-228.
- MÉNDEZ-ALZOLA R. 1941. — El *Smilodon bonaerensis* (Muñiz): estudio osteológico y osteométrico del gran tigre fósil de La Pampa comparado con otros félidos actuales y fósiles. *Anales del Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales "Bernardino Rivadavia"*, Buenos Aires 40 (67): 135-252.
- MERRIAM J. C. & STOCK C. 1932. — The Felidae of Rancho La Brea. *Carnegie Institution of Washington Publications* 422: 1-231.
- METCALF J., TURNEY C., BARNETT R., MARTIN F., BRAY S., VILSTRUP J., ORLANDO L., SALAS-GISMONDI R., LOPONTE D., MEDINA M., DE NIGRIS M., CIVALERO T., FERNÁNDEZ P., GASCO A., DURAN V., SEYMOUR K., OTAOLA C., GIL A., PAUNERO R., PREVOSTI F., BRADSHAW C., WHEELER J., BORRERO L., AUSTIN J. & COOPER A. 2016. — Synergistic roles of climate warming and human occupation in Patagonian megafaunal extinctions during the Last Deglaciation. *Science Advances* 2 (6): 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1501682>
- MONES A. & RINDERKNECHT A. 2004. — The first South American Homotheriini (Mammalia: Carnivora: Felidae). *Comunicaciones Paleontológicas del Museo Nacional de Historia Natural y Antropología* 35 (2): 201-212.
- MONTELLANO-BALLESTEROS M. & CARBOT-CHANONA G. 2009. — *Panthera leo atrox* (Mammalia: Carnivora: Felidae) in Chiapas, Mexico. *The Southwestern Naturalist* 54 (2): 217-222. <https://doi.org/10.1894/CLG-20.1>

- MORALES-MEJÍA F. M., ARROYO-CABRALES J. & POLACO O. J. 2010. — Estudio comparativo de algunos elementos de las extremidades anteriores y posteriores y piezas dentales de puma (*Puma concolor*) y jaguar (*Panthera onca*). *Revista Especializada en Ciencias Químico-Biológicas* 13 (2): 73-90.
- MORENO A. M. & LIMA-RIBEIRO M. S. 2015. — Ecological niche models, fossil record and the multi-temporal calibration for *Panthera onca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Mammalia: Felidae). *Brazilian Journal of Biological Sciences* 2 (4): 309-319.
- PAYÁN GARRIDO E. & SOTO VARGAS C. 2012. — *Los Felinos de Colombia*. Ministerio de Ambiente y Desarrollo Sostenible, Instituto de Investigaciones de Recursos Biológicos Alexander von Humboldt y Panthera Colombia. Ediprint Ltda., Bogotá, 48 p.
- PEREIRA-GARBERO R. & SAPP A. 2016. — Historia del jaguar en Uruguay y la Banda Oriental, in MEDELLÍN R., DE LA TORRE A., ZARZA H., CHÁVEZ C. & CEBALLOS G. (eds), *El jaguar en el siglo XXI. La perspectiva continental*. FCE, UNAM - Instituto de Ecología, México: 479-494.
- PEREIRA-GARBERO R., BARRENECHE J., LAUFER G., ACHAVAL F. & ARIM M. 2013. — Mamíferos invasores en Uruguay, historia, perspectivas y consecuencias. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural* 86 (4): 403-421. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0716-078X2013000400003>
- PERRI A. R., MITCHELL K. J. & MOUTON A. [...] & FRANTZ L. A. F. 2021. — Dire wolves were the last of an ancient New World canid lineage. *Nature* 591: 87-91. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-03082-x>
- PREVOSTI F. & VIZCAÍNO S. 2006. — Paleocology of the large carnivore guild from the late Pleistocene of Argentina. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 51 (3): 407-422.
- PREVOSTI F. & MARTIN F. 2013. — Paleocology of the mammalian predator guild of Southern Patagonia during the latest Pleistocene: ecomorphology, stable isotopes, and taphonomy. *Quaternary International* 305: 74-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2012.12.039>
- PREVOSTI F. & FORASIEPI A. 2018. — *Evolution of South American Mammalian Predators During the Cenozoic: Paleobiogeographic and Paleoenvironmental Contingencies*. Springer Geology, Switzerland, 196 p.
- PREVOSTI F., UBILLA M. & PEREA D. 2009. — Large extinct canids from the Pleistocene of Uruguay: systematic, biogeographic and paleoecological remarks. *Historical Biology* 21 (1): 79-89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912960903249337>
- RICHARD E. 2005. — *Introducción al conocimiento de los felinos (Mammalia: Felidae) de Argentina y Bolivia, con especial referencia al estatus en Argentina*. Cátedra de Zoología General: Materiales de Estudio. Carrera de Ingeniería Ambiental, Escuela Militar de Ingeniería, La Paz, 139 p.
- RINCÓN A., PREVOSTI F. & PARRA G. 2011. — New saber-toothed cats records (Felidae: Machairodontinae) for the Pleistocene of Venezuela, and the Great American Biotic Interchange. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 31 (2): 468-478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.2011.550366>
- RODRIGUES S., AVILLA L., SOIBELZON L. & BERNARDES C. 2014. — Late Pleistocene carnivores (Carnivora: Mammalia) from a cave sedimentary deposit in northern Brazil. *Anais da Academia Brasileira de Ciências* 86 (4): 1641-1655. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765201420140314>
- RODRIGUEZ S., MÉNDEZ C., SOIBELZON E., SOIBELZON L. H., CONTRERAS S., FRIEDRICH S., LUNA C. & ZURITA A. 2018. — *Panthera onca* (Carnivora, Felidae) in the late Pleistocene-early Holocene of northern Argentina. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Palaontologie Monatshefte* 289 (2): 177-187. <https://doi.org/10.1127/njgpa/2018/0758>
- ROMERO-MUÑOZ A., MAFFEI L., CUÉLLAR E. & NOSS A. 2010. — Temporal separation between jaguar and puma in the dry forests of southern Bolivia. *Journal of Tropical Ecology* 26 (3): 303-311.
- RUEDA P., MENDOZA G. D., MARTÍNEZ D. & ROSAS-ROSAS O. C. 2013. — Determination of the jaguar (*Panthera onca*) and puma (*Puma concolor*) diet in a tropical forest in San Luis Potosí, Mexico. *Journal of Applied Animal Research* 41 (4): 484-489. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09712119.2013.787362>
- RUIZ-RAMONI D., MONTELLANO-BALLESTEROS M., ARROYO-CABRALES J., CASO A. & CARVAJAL-VILLARREAL S. 2020. — The large jaguar that lived in the past of México: a forgotten fossil. *Therya* 11 (1): 33-40. <https://doi.org/10.12933/therya-20-821>
- SCHALLER G. B. 2009. — *The Serengeti lion: a study of predator-prey relations*. University of Chicago Press., Chicago, 480 p.
- SEYMOUR K. 1989. — *Panthera onca*. *Mammalian Species* 340: 9 p. <https://doi.org/10.2307/13504096>
- SHOCKEY B., SALAS-GISMONDI R., BABY P., GUYOT J., BALTAZAR M., HUAMÁN L., CLACK A., STUCCHI M., PUJOS F., EMERSON J. & FLYNN J. 2009. — New Pleistocene Cave Faunas of the Andes of Central Perú: Radiocarbon Ages and the Survival of Low Latitude, Pleistocene DNA. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 12 (3), 15 p.
- SMITH R. 1993. — Bias in equations used to estimate fossil primate body mass. *Journal of Human Evolution* 25 (1): 31-41. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhev.1993.1036>
- SOIBELZON L. & PREVOSTI F. 2007. — Los carnívoros (Carnivora, Mammalia) terrestres del Cuaternario de América del Sur. *Monografías de la Societat D'Historia Natural de Les Balears* 14: 49-68.
- SOIBELZON L. & PREVOSTI F. 2013. — Fossil of South American land carnivores (Carnivora, Mammalia), in RUIZ-GARCÍA M. & SHOSTELL J. M. (eds), *Molecular population genetics, evolutionary biology and biological conservation of Neotropical carnivores*. Nova Science Publishers, Inc., New York: 509-527.
- SUNQUIST M. E. & SUNQUIST F. C. 2009. — Family Felidae (cats), in WILSON D. & MITTERMEIER R. (eds), *Handbook of the mammals of the world*. Vol. 1. *Carnivores*. Lynx Ediciones, Barcelona: 54-168.
- SWANK W. & TEER J. 1989. — Status of the jaguar 1987. *Oryx* 23 (1): 14-21. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605300022547>
- THACKERAY J. & KIESER J. 1992. — Body mass and carnassial length in modern and fossil carnivores. *Annals of the Transvaal Museum* 35 (24): 337-341.
- THOMAS O. 1911. — The mammals of the tenth edition of Linnaeus: an attempt to fix the types of the genera and the exact bases and localities of the specimens. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 81: 120-158.
- UBILLA M. & PEREA D. 1999. — Quaternary vertebrates of Uruguay: a biostratigraphic, biogeographic and climatic overview. *Quaternary of South America and Antarctic Peninsula* 12: 75-90.
- UBILLA M. & MARTÍNEZ S. 2016. — *Geology and Paleontology of the Quaternary of Uruguay*. SpringerBriefs in Earth System Sciences, Switzerland, 82 p. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29303-5>
- UBILLA M., PEREA D., GOSO AGUILAR C. & LORENZO N. 2004. — Late Pleistocene vertebrates from northern Uruguay: tools for biostratigraphic, climatic and environmental reconstruction. *Quaternary International* 114 (1): 129-142. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(03\)00048-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(03)00048-X)
- UBILLA M., PEREA D., LORENZO N., GUTIÉRREZ M. & RINDERKNECHT A. 2011. — Fauna Cuaternaria Continental, in PEREA D. (ed.), *Fósiles de Uruguay*. Edición D.I.R.A.C., Facultad de Ciencias, Montevideo: 283-314.
- UBILLA M., CORONA A., RINDERKNECHT A., PEREA D. & VERDE M. 2016. — Marine isotope Stage 3 (MIS 3) and continental beds of northern Uruguay (Sopas Formation): paleontology, chronology and climate, in GASPARINI G., RABASSA J., DESCHAMPS C. & TONNI E. (eds), *Marine Isotope Stage 3 in Southern South America, 60 ka B.P.-30 ka B.P.* Springer International Publishing, Basel: 183-205. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40000-6_11
- UBILLA M., RINDERKNECHT A., CORONA A. & PEREA D. 2018. — Mammals in last 30 to 7 ka interval (late Pleistocene-early Holocene) in southern Uruguay (Santa Lucía River Basin): last occurrences, climate and biogeography. *Journal of Mammalian*

- Evolution* 25: 291-300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10914-017-9380-2>
- VAN VALKENBURGH B. 1990. — Skeletal and dental predictors of body mass in carnivores, in DAMUTH J. & MACFADDEN B. J. (eds), *Body Size in Mammalian Paleobiology: Estimation and Biological Implication*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge: 181-205.
- VAN VALKENBURGH B. 1991. — Iterative evolution of hypercarnivory in canid (Mammalia: Carnivora): evolutionary interactions among sympatric predators. *Paleobiology* 17 (4): 340-362. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0094837300010691>
- VON DEN DRIESCH A. 1976. — *A guide to the measurement of animal bones from archaeological sites*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge (MA), 136 p.
- WERDELIN L., YAMAGUCHI N., JOHNSON W. E. & O'BRIEN S. J. 2010. — Phylogeny and evolution of cats (Felidae), in MACDONALD D. W. & LOVERIDGE A. J. (eds), *Biology and Conservation of Wild Felids*. Oxford University Press, Oxford: 59-82.
- WOODBURNE M. O. 2010. — The Great American Biotic Interchange: Dispersals, Tectonics, Climate, Sea Level and Holding Pens. *Journal of Mammalian Evolution* 17: 245-264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10914-010-9144-8>
- ZARRATE-CHARRY D., LAVERDE TRUJILLO L., BALAGUERA-REINA S., GONZÁLEZ-MAYA J. & TRUJILLO F. 2009. — Rescate y manejo de fauna silvestre ex situ en Colombia: estudio de caso de un jaguar (*Panthera onca*) en la orinoquía colombiana. *Revista CES-Medicina Veterinaria y Zootecnia* 4 (1): 81-89.

*Submitted on 13 March 2021;
accepted on 1 June 2021;
published on 8 September 2022.*

APPENDICES. — Supplementary materials.

APPENDIX 1. — Body mass equations used in this article.

Body mass equations (in kg) for felids according to Van Valkenburgh (1990). Measurements in mm. %PE, percent prediction error:

– based on antero-posterior diameter of the m1 (m1AP)
 $\log \text{body mass} = 3.05 \times \log \text{m1AP} - 2.15$; %PE 29.72

Body mass equations (in kg) for felids according to Thackeray & Kieser (1992). Measurements in mm. %PE, percent prediction error:

– based on antero-posterior diameter of the m1 (m1AP)
 $\log \text{body mass} = 3.37 \times \log \text{m1AP} - 2.57$; %PE 27.73

Body mass equations (in kg) of the typical prey (TPM) and the maximum prey (MPM) for extant felids following Prevosti & Vizcaíno (2006). *M* is the body mass (in kg) of the carnivorous mammal. %PE, percent prediction error; *r*, coefficient of correlation:

$\log \text{body mass TPM} = 1.86 \times \log M - 1.74$; %PE, 77.73; *r*, 0.9
 $\log \text{body mass MPM} = 1.29 \times \log M + 0.075$; %PE, 15.23; *r*, 0.88

Body mass equations (in kg) of the typical prey (TPM) and the maximum prey (MPM) for extant felids following Prevosti & Martin (2013). *M* is the body mass (in kg) of the carnivorous mammal. %PE, percent prediction error; *r*, coefficient of correlation:

$\log \text{body mass TPM} = 1.54 \times \log M - 0.92$; %PE 54.55; *r*, 0.9
 $\log \text{body mass MPM} = 1.00 \times \log M + 0.69$; %PE 35.02; *r*, 0.88

Body mass equation (in kg) of the typical prey (TPM) for extant felids following Hemmer (2007). *M* is the body mass (in kg) of the carnivorous mammal:

$\log \text{body mass TPM} = 1.917 \times \log M - 1.710$

APPENDIX 2. — Measurements used in this article: **1**, TL; **2**, Hm1; **3**, Bm1; **4**, TRLc-m1; **5**, cAP; **6**, cML; **7**, p3AP; **8**, p3ML; **9**, p4AP; **10**, p4ML; **11**, m1AP; **12**, m1ML. Abbreviations: **Bm1**, breadth of the mandible at the posterior border of the m1; **cAP**, antero-posterior diameter of the canine; **cML**, transverse diameter of the canine; **Hm1**, height of the mandible at the posterior border of the m1; **m1 AP**, antero-posterior diameter of the m1; **m1 ML**, transverse diameter of the m1; **p3AP**, antero-posterior diameter of the p3; **p3ML**, transverse diameter of the p3; **p4AP**, antero-posterior diameter of the p4; **p4ML**, transverse diameter of the p4; **TL**, total length; **TRL c-m1**, tooth row length canine-m1.

1

